

Agency amidst adversity: Female migrants, social constraints, and the spirit of Ubuntu

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Abstract

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Migration is often viewed as a pathway to empowerment and improved livelihoods, particularly for women seeking economic opportunities in urban settings. However, internal female migrants frequently encounter significant social constraints that undermine their agency and limit their ability to fully participate in decision-making processes that affect their lives. This paper examines the interplay between women's agency and social constraints among female migrants in Ondangwa, Namibia, a town that serves as a hub for internal migration within the country. Grounded in the philosophy of Ubuntu, which emphasizes interconnectedness, communal support, and collective well-being, this study explores how these women navigate systemic barriers while fostering resilience and mutual empowerment within their communities. Drawing on qualitative data collected through in-depth interviews, thematic analysis was used to identify recurring patterns and themes related to social constraints, agency, and resilience. The study reveals that female migrants in Ondangwa navigate a complex web of challenges, including patriarchal structures, economic dependency, and cultural expectations that often restrict their autonomy. These constraints are compounded by limited access to resources and discriminatory practices, which hinder their ability to contribute meaningfully to family and community life—a core tenet of Ubuntu's ethos of "I am because we are." Despite these systemic barriers, the findings highlight the remarkable resilience and resourcefulness of these women as they assert their agency. Drawing on communal networks and shared experiences, respondents demonstrated how principles of Ubuntu, such as solidarity, mutual aid, and collective responsibility, enable them to overcome adversity. For instance, informal networks of support among migrant women serve as critical safety nets, providing emotional, social, and economic assistance in times of need. Additionally, women employ diverse strategies, including economic entrepreneurship, cultural negotiation, and community mobilization, to challenge restrictive norms and reshape their social realities in alignment with Ubuntu's values of inclusivity and shared humanity. Ultimately, the study underscores the importance of recognizing and supporting women's agency as a critical factor in fostering inclusive and equitable societies. By addressing the root causes of marginalization and implementing targeted, Ubuntu-aligned interventions, policymakers and stakeholders can create an enabling environment where migrant women can thrive, contributing not only to their own well-being but also to the broader socio-economic development of their host communities.

Key words

Internal migration, women's agency, social constraints, gender-based violence, empowerment, Ubuntu.

1. Introduction

The role that women play in society has significantly expanded in recent years, largely driven by the rise in women's agency and empowerment (Khader, 2018a). As women gain greater autonomy and influence, they increasingly challenge traditional gender roles and contribute to societal advancements, though challenges remain in fully implementing and enforcing supportive policies.

Despite the increase in laws and frameworks advocating for women's empowerment, gaps remain in their implementation and enforcement, particularly in contexts where women continue to face marginalization (World Bank, 2021). These gaps are evident in the context of internal migration, where women relocating from rural to urban areas often encounter a double bind of traditional gender norms and new urban pressures, (Patel, 2024). Economic disparities and limited access to resources, restrict, however women's ability to exercise agency over their lives (Lwamba et al., 2022), leaving women, particularly migrant women, vulnerable to various social and cultural challenges.

The International Labour Organization (2018) (ILO) emphasizes that migrant women, who make up a significant portion of internal migrants, often face discrimination, disrespect, and a lack of dignity. They are frequently not recognized for their potential to make valuable contributions to economies. Additionally, migrant women are subject to stereotypes such as that they are uneducated, dependent, and primarily suited for menial, low-paying or caregiving jobs. These stereotypes suggest they are incapable of independent decision-making or entrepreneurial work, which limits their opportunities for formal employment. As a result, they are often forced to work within invisible or informal economies, exposing them to risks such as human trafficking, indecent work, exploitation, and extortion, all of which strip them of their dignity,

Although data on internal migration levels in Africa is scarce, countries like South Africa, Zambia, and Namibia have shown higher levels of internal migration within the Southern African region (Elridge, 2022). These movements are often driven by the pursuit of improved livelihoods, access to resources, and opportunities for socio-economic advancement (Venditto, 2019). However, internal migration also brings challenges, particularly for women who face systemic barriers such as patriarchal norms, rigid gender roles, and employment segregation that constrain their agency and limit their ability to thrive in new environments. These social constraints highlight a disconnection from the core values of interconnectedness, mutual support, and collective well-being often associated with the African ethos of "*Ubuntu ngumuntu ngabantu*"¹ which instead emphasizes the importance of community solidarity and shared responsibility in fostering equitable societies. Yet, patriarchal structures and discriminatory practices often marginalize women, undermining their capacity to contribute meaningfully to family and community life—a central tenet of Ubuntu. For instance, restrictive gender roles perpetuate inequality by confining women to traditional domestic spheres, while employment segregation limits their access to economic opportunities that could empower them and uplift their households.

It is within this context that this study seeks to investigate how these social constraints impact women's agency among internal migrants in Ondangwa, Namibia. By drawing on Ubuntu's principles of inclusivity, communal resilience, and shared humanity, the research aims to explore not only the challenges faced by migrant women but also the ways in which they leverage communal networks and solidarity to assert their agency. Ultimately, this inquiry aligns with Ubuntu's call for transformative change, advocating for policies and interventions that dismantle systemic barriers and promote gender equity, thereby enabling women to fulfil their potential as active agents of development within their communities.

The paper is structured as follows: In Section two, the paper underscores the significant progress women have made in recent years in terms of agency and empowerment. It highlights broader societal advancements driven by women challenging traditional gender roles while simultaneously identifying gaps in policy implementation and enforcement that leave women, particularly migrant women, vulnerable to marginalization. Section three delves into the tension between patriarchal structures and Ubuntu's core values of interconnectedness, mutual support, and collective well-being. This section sets the stage for exploring how migrant women navigate social constraints while asserting their agency within the framework of Ubuntu philosophy. Section four outlines the methodology, detailing the qualitative approach and exploratory research design employed to examine the lived experiences of internal migrant women in Ondangwa. The section explains the use of in-depth interviews and thematic analysis to uncover recurring patterns and themes related to social constraints and resilience. Section five presents and discuss the study's findings, which reveal the challenges faced by migrant women, including discrimination, economic disparities, and limited access

¹ "A human being is a human being through other human beings" often translated into "I am because we are" (Ramose, 2002 p. 41).

to resources. It also highlights their resilience and the role of communal networks in overcoming adversity. The findings are integrated with Ubuntu philosophy, offering a deeper analysis of how communal solidarity and shared humanity can address systemic barriers. The paper concludes with Section seven which summarizes the key insights and provides actionable recommendations. These recommendations, rooted in Ubuntu principles, advocate for transformative policies and community-based initiatives to dismantle systemic barriers and empower migrant women as active agents of development within their communities.

2. Progress and persistent challenges in women's empowerment

Global efforts to advance women's agency and empowerment have been made in recent years. This progress is evident in the increasing participation of women in education, which is a critical driver of women's agency, enabling access to economic opportunities and fostering critical consciousness. Gender parity in education has seen significant milestones globally: primary and lower secondary education enrolment reached parity in 2009, upper secondary education followed suit in 2013, and tertiary education achieved parity as early as 1998. However, Sub-Saharan Africa remains an exception, as gender parity has yet to be achieved at any educational level despite notable progress. Globally, disparities persist in specific areas such as STEM fields and leadership roles. In 2022, women held fewer than 25% of jobs in science, engineering, and ICT sectors and occupied just over one-fifth of technology-related positions in companies (UNESCO, 2024), underscoring enduring biases in educational and professional pathways.

Women's labor force participation has grown steadily, yet structural inequities persist. Globally, women continue to face significant economic disparities, as they earn 20% less than men and are often concentrated in lower-paying jobs and underrepresented in higher-paying industries, (United Nations Women, 2024). The disparity is even more pronounced in certain regions, such as Sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia, where cultural norms and limited access to education further exacerbate income inequality. Moreover, the lack of representation in leadership roles compounds these challenges. Despite making up nearly half of the global workforce, women occupy only 28% of managerial positions worldwide. In industries such as technology and finance, this figure drops significantly, with women holding just 15% of senior leadership roles (McKinsey & Company, 2024).

On the other hand, looking at women political representation the Inter Parliamentary Union indicates that in the last three decades, the percentage of seats held by women has risen from 11.3% in 1995 to 27.2% in 2025, although men still outnumber women by more than three times in executive and legislative positions, with a decline of women in government position by 0.4% (Inter Parliamentary Union, 2025; UN Woman, 2025).

These disparities highlight the pervasive influence of systemic biases and discriminatory practices that hinder women's career advancement. This also shows that while progress has been made, women ability to challenge traditional gender roles that have historically confined them to domestic spheres is still difficult (Khader, 2018b). Women's empowerment must, in fact considered and assessed not merely as an individual achievement but as a collective process that involves dismantling structural barriers and fostering equitable opportunities for all women, particularly those from marginalized communities. Furthermore, these gains remain uneven across regions and socioeconomic groups, and substantial gaps remain in the implementation and enforcement of policies designed to support women's empowerment and promote gender equality, (World Bank, 2021). For instance, discriminatory practices persist in areas such as property rights, access to credit, and labor market participation, disproportionately affecting women in vulnerable situations. More relevant is the observation that empowerment is not merely the absence of discrimination but the presence of agency: the ability to make strategic life choices and challenge systemic inequities (Kabeer, 2005). The case of internal migrant women is particularly illustrative of these challenges.

Migrant women constitute nearly half of the international migrant population, with many seeking better economic opportunities, safety from conflict, or reunification with family members (United Nations Women, 2016a). They often exhibit resilience and resourcefulness, navigating complex migration processes despite facing multiple barriers. A significant proportion of these women migrate internally, moving from rural areas to urban centres in search of employment, education, and improved living standards (Pickbourn, 2018). Internal migration, often driven by the pursuit of improved livelihoods, exposes women to unique vulnerabilities. This movement can be viewed as the outcome of a plan developed by the person and/or her family to react to outside forces or to deal with challenges and constraints they face in their place of origin (Venditto, 2019). As noted by Patel (2024), migrant women frequently encounter a double bind of traditional gender norms and new urban pressures. These include economic disparities, limited access to resources, and systemic barriers such as patriarchal structures and rigid gender roles. Such constraints severely restrict women's ability to exercise agency over their lives, leaving them susceptible to marginalization and exploitation. Lwamba et al. (2022) document how internal migrant women in sub-Saharan Africa often face exclusion from formal

employment due to entrenched stereotypes about their capabilities and roles. These stereotypes—such as the perception that women are primarily suited for caregiving or menial jobs—limit their opportunities for upward mobility and reinforce cycles of poverty. Furthermore, the informal economies in which many migrant women are forced to operate expose them to risks such as human trafficking, indecent work conditions, and extortion, further stripping them of their dignity and agency.

This overview underscores the dual narrative of progress and persistent challenges in women's empowerment. While women have made strides in challenging traditional gender roles and contributing to societal advancements, systemic barriers continue to hinder their full participation in social, economic, and political spheres. The intersection of gender and migration amplifies these challenges, necessitating a deeper exploration of how migrant women navigate social constraints while asserting their agency. This sets the stage for the subsequent sections, which examine these dynamics through the lens of Ubuntu philosophy and empirical evidence from Ondangwa, Namibia.

3. Ubuntu's core values and women's migration

Ubuntu, rooted in the principle "I am because we are", emphasizes interconnectedness, mutual support, and collective well-being; it underscores the importance of community solidarity and shared responsibility in fostering equitable societies (Tutu, 1999). For women migrants, particularly those in a context of displacement, economic insecurity, and systemic discrimination, these values offer both a survival framework and a lens to challenge structural inequities.

Many migrant women come from impoverished regions where economic opportunities are scarce, prompting them to seek livelihoods elsewhere (International Organization for Migration (IOM), 2020). They are often young and of working age, motivated by the prospect of better employment and the ability to support their families financially. However, the migration journey and settlement process can be fraught with challenges, including discrimination, legal restrictions, and limited access to social services (International Labour Organization, 2018). Additionally, migrant women frequently play dual roles as earners and caregivers, balancing the demands of work with family responsibilities, which can exacerbate their vulnerability and stress levels (Tawodzera, 2024). The African continent has witnessed significant rural-to-urban migration as women seek to escape poverty, lack of infrastructure, and limited access to social services in rural areas (United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), 2022). Characteristics of internal migrant women in Africa includes a mix of young, single women and those with families. They often have lower levels of formal education, which limits their job prospects to low-skilled and informal sectors (Anyidoho, 2020). Precarious employment, inadequate housing, and social isolation are often what migrants' women have to face with, (United Nations Women, 2016a, 2016b), Despite these adversities, migrant women display remarkable resilience and adaptability, finding ways to survive and support their families through entrepreneurial activities and informal labour. Studies highlight how women in an alien and hostile environment, relay on social capital, usually relatives already settled in host countries, to provide critical resources such as housing, childcare, and share information about jobs, (Raniga & Fitshane, 2022; Venditto et al. 2023). Such practices align with Ubuntu's ethos that relational bonds and mutual aid enable collective well-being; as observed by Kruidenir (2015) in informal settlements, migrant women engage in mutual support practices that embody Ubuntu's ethos. This collectivism enables migrant women to mitigate economic precarity through resource-pooling initiatives such as savings groups and peer networks. These networks not only safeguard their livelihoods, protecting market stalls and children while they work, but also reinforce communal welfare as integral to individual survival (Kruidenir, 2015). Conversely, isolation from such networks often exacerbates vulnerability, hindering access to stable livelihoods.

On the other hand, these practices also reflect Ubuntu's emphasis on collective responsibility, where individual survival is tied to communal welfare, while lacking supportive relationships, leave the individual isolated and unable to secure stable livelihoods. This vision of collective well-being intersects with feminist movements advocating for migrant women's rights. In West and Central Africa, the feminist movements, embracing the principles of Ubuntu, are focusing on collective empowerment and communal well-being, to address the complexities of gender inequality, violence, and discrimination, Women Leaders Network for development (2025). By standing together, women can, in fact challenge the systemic inequalities that perpetuate violence and discrimination, particular evident in the case of migrant women facing exploitation in sectors like domestic work or street vending.

3.1. Migrant women in Namibia

In Namibia, internal migration has undergone significant changes over time. During the colonial era, internal migration was predominantly characterized by male movement, driven by contract labour systems. Men often migrated from rural areas to work in minefields, farms, and factories, while women largely remained in rural regions, managing households

and agricultural duties. This pattern reflected the economic and social structures of the time, with men seeking labour opportunities in urban centres or industrial sites.

Following Namibia's independence in 1990, migration patterns shifted significantly. The end of the colonial era, combined with new economic and educational opportunities, led to a more diverse trend in internal migration. Women increasingly moved from rural areas to urban centres in search of better economic prospects, improved living standards, and access to education. This shift was largely motivated by the need to escape the limited economic opportunities and harsh living conditions prevalent in rural areas (Venditto, 2018). The growing labour opportunities and the promise of enhanced living conditions in urban centres became a key incentive for many women, transforming the demographic and socio-economic landscape of internal migration in Namibia (Pendleton et al., 2014). According to the Namibia Statistics Agency (2011), between 2001 and 2011, the proportion of internal migrants at regional level increased from 19.6 to 22.5 percent. Currently, almost 1 million people or 32 % of the population reside in a place different from the place of birth (Namibia Statistic Agency, 2024). The characteristics of migrant women in Namibia, shaped by factors such as age, socioeconomic status, and educational background, reveal that many are young and of working age, with a significant proportion having limited formal education. This often confines them to low-wage, informal employment, such as domestic work, caregiving, and street vending (Olivier, 2016). However, traditional gender roles remain influential, and systemic barriers—including discriminatory practices and inadequate policies—continue to restrict women's agency and economic mobility.

To contextualize these trends within the specific field case, the presence of migrant women² in Ondangwa must be considered. The town located in the Oshana Region of northern Namibia, approximately 60 kilometres north of the regional capital, Oshakati, serves as a commercial hub for agricultural produce and livestock. Ondangwa features various businesses and services and is well-connected by road, rail, and an airport that provides regional air connectivity. Despite these infrastructural advantages, Ondangwa still faces socio-economic challenges, including high unemployment and inadequate infrastructure in certain areas, which directly impact the daily lives of its residents. Given the lack of official statistics on their exact numbers, a conservative estimate can be derived from the most recent population census. With an internal migration rate of 32% and a total population of 31,466 in Ondangwa, approximately 10,070 residents are estimated to have been born elsewhere. Based on the gender ratio in the town, an estimated 5,342 of these migrants are female (Namibia Statistics Agency, 2024). The field case analysis of Ondangwa provides an opportunity to explore the lived experiences of migrant women, shedding light on their economic roles, challenges, and contributions to the town's development

4. Methodology

For this study, a qualitative approach together with an exploratory research design was used, allowing for in-depth understanding and rich description of the phenomena. The population was represented by the internal migrant women of Ondangwa. A total of 12 migrant women were selected which represented the point of saturation. This number is regarded as adequate for qualitative studies by authors such as Hennink & Kaiser (2022) who recommend a sample of between 9 – 17 for qualitative studies to reach saturation. The non-probability sampling method, specifically snowball sampling, was used in this study because it was particularly effective for accessing hard-to-reach or hidden populations. This method relies on referrals from initial participants to recruit further subjects, which was beneficial in identifying migrant women who may not be easily accessible through conventional sampling techniques.

In-depth face-to-face interviews were conducted using an interview guide with open-ended questions in line with the research questions and the study objectives. Additionally, open-ended questions encouraged respondents to express their thoughts and feelings in their own words, providing a deeper understanding of their lived experiences and the contextual factors influencing their agency power. The questions focused on exploring the types of difficulties and constraints individuals encountered during their migratory experiences, as well as how they addressed these challenges. Special attention was given to understanding how forced patriarchal norms and entrenched traditions influenced their journeys and decision-making processes. Participants were asked to reflect on the specific obstacles they faced—whether economic, social, cultural, or legal—and to describe the strategies they employed to navigate or overcome these hurdles. By examining these dimensions, the aim was to shed light on the intersectional nature of migration challenges and the resilience of individuals in confronting systemic inequalities.

Although the sample size was sufficient for qualitative studies, it may not have fully capture the diversity of experiences among migrant women. Migrant women come from various cultural, socio-economic, educational, and geographic

² In this context we consider internal migrants those individuals who were born in place different from Ondangwa.

backgrounds, and the selected participants might not have adequately represent the broader population of migrant women. This may have affected the depth, breadth, and generalizability of the findings.

Permission to conduct the study was obtained from the University of Namibia Research Ethics Committee. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents, ensuring they understood the nature of the study, the confidentiality, and how the data was to be used (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The interviews were conducted at the premises of the respondents where they were comfortable to facilitate a relaxed and open conversation. Each interview was recorded with the respondent's consent, and field notes were taken to capture non-verbal cues and contextual details that might not be evident in the audio recordings alone. This dual approach enhanced the richness and accuracy of the data collected. The interviews lasted between 40 to 60 minutes each and were conducted over a period of six weeks between July and August 2024. This timeline allowed for flexibility in scheduling and ensured that the researcher could adapt to the respondent's availability. Once this process was completed, the data was readied for analysis. Thematic analysis was used to analyse the data collected in this study, (Nowell et al., 2017). This method ensured a methodical and transparent analysis, allowing the identification of key themes and subthemes that offer deep insights into the effects of social constraints on women's agency power.

5. Findings and discussion

This section starts by examining demographic and socioeconomic patterns among respondents. Table 5 paints a vivid picture of the lives and trajectories of individuals navigating the complexities of modern Namibia, revealing key trends in age distribution, migration dynamics, marital status, and educational attainment. The majority of respondents fall within the 25-30 age group, a demographic often described as the backbone of economically active populations. This aligns with findings from the Namibia Statistics Agency (2015), which highlights this age bracket as a critical driver of labour market participation. These are the years when individuals are most likely to seek stable employment, pursue career advancement, or migrate in search of better prospects.

Migration patterns further illuminate these aspirations. Respondents' movements from less developed regions—such as Omusati and Ohangwena—to urban centres like Ondangwa underscore the pull of economic activity and employment prospects. Ondangwa, with its burgeoning infrastructure and commercial hubs, has become a magnet for those seeking to escape rural poverty or underemployment. Yet, this migration is not merely about geography; it reflects broader social transformations. Moving to urban areas often means leaving behind familiar support networks, traditional ways of life, and cultural anchors.

The data on marital status adds another layer to this narrative. Most respondents were single, particularly those in the younger age groups, while married individuals were concentrated among older cohorts (above 40). This suggests that marriage is increasingly being delayed—a trend observed globally but amplified in contexts where economic stability is a prerequisite for starting a family. For many young migrants, the decision to postpone marriage may also be linked to their migratory journeys. Leaving home often disrupts traditional timelines for life transitions, including settling down or starting families. In some cases, this delay reflects a conscious choice to prioritize education and career over familial obligations, signalling shifts in societal values and expectations.

Educational attainment emerges as one of the standout features of this dataset. A significant proportion of respondents hold university degrees, reflecting a highly educated cohort poised to contribute meaningfully to Namibia's development. This high level of education correlates strongly with full-time employment rates, underscoring the importance of tertiary qualifications in accessing formal job markets. Notably, the unemployment rate among respondents is relatively low compared to national averages, suggesting that higher education serves as a buffer against unemployment in this sample.

Table 5.1 Demographic and socio-economic information

	Age Group	Place of Birth	Year of arrival	Marital Status	No. of children	Education Level	Occupation
1	25 - 30	Ondangwa (Rural)	2015	Single	2	Secondary	Sales person
2	36 - 40	Uukwangula village	2006	Married	4	University degree/Above	Employed fulltime
3	25 - 30	Eloolo	2022	Single	Yes	University degree/Above	Teacher
4	25 - 30	Epyalyipundu	2022	Single	-	Diploma/Certificate	Unemployed
5	25 - 30	Swakopmund	2019	Married	1	University degree/Above	Teacher
6	36 - 40	Okalongo	2022	Single	2	University degree/Above	Teacher
7	31 - 35	Onampadhi-Oniipa	2017	Single	2	University degree/Above	Teacher
8	25 - 30	Oshikondilango	2019	Single	-	Secondary	Cashier
9	25 - 30	Ludiritz	2016	Single	-	Secondary	Sales person
10	Above 45	Okankelo	1996	Married	3	Secondary	Unemployed/market seller
11	31 - 35	Ondobe	2018	Single	1	Vocational training	Woodwork/carpentry
12	Below 25	Oshatolwa	2024	Single	1	Secondary	Unemployed

Source: Field data (2024)

Three key themes emerged from the respondents' narratives: i) *pursuit of improved socio-economic status* with codes such as escape poverty, job opportunities, better services; ii) *socio-economic constraints* with codes such as discrimination and exclusion, limited access to resources and services, cultural constraints iii) *navigating social barriers to women's agency*, with codes such as active advocacy and participation, networking, economic empowerment, supportive social programs and policy reforms.

These themes collectively illustrate the complex interplay between aspiration, adversity, and agency. While the pursuit of improved socio-economic status serves as a powerful motivator for migration and personal advancement, systemic constraints pose significant hurdles. However, the determination and strategic actions of women demonstrate how individuals can navigate and challenge societal barriers to carve out pathways for empowerment and progress. This aligns with the Ubuntu ideal of striving for collective well-being, as individuals seek not only personal advancement but also opportunities to uplift their families and communities. At the same time the determination and strategic actions of women demonstrate how individuals can harness communal networks and advocate for systemic change to overcome adversity.

5.1 Pursuit of Improved Socio-Economic Status

This theme captures the motivations driving migration, with respondents emphasizing their desire to escape poverty, secure stable employment, and access improved services such as healthcare, education, and infrastructure. The attraction of urban centres lies in their perceived economic vibrancy and the availability of resources that are often lacking in rural or less developed areas. This pursuit underscores the critical role that socio-economic aspirations play in shaping mobility patterns and decision-making.

The respondents reported that the scarcity of employment opportunities in their rural environments severely limited their capacity to attain financial security. Consequently, relocating to urban centres such as Ondangwa provided them with access to a wider range of job opportunities. Their migration narratives were strongly driven by aspirations for economic autonomy, self-sufficiency, and professional advancement. For instance, respondent 5 emphasized that her rural community lacked viable employment avenues, and this pervasive economic stagnation ultimately prompted her decision to seek opportunities elsewhere.

“I moved to Ondangwa because I stay in a rural area where there is no opportunity to work or better training centre.”

Similarly, respondent 9 explained that while opportunities back home were scarce, the town offered various employment possibilities that could improve her financial standing:

“...in Ondangwa there are more job opportunities.”

The aspiration to overcome poverty was a persistent element in respondents’ narratives, underscoring how economic deprivation in their former environments acted as a central catalyst for migration. Respondent 4, for example, detailed how lack of viable opportunities impeded her ability to secure essential resources, ultimately propelling her to relocate.

“Where I come from, there are very few ways to make money. I had to move here to escape the poverty and try to find work to support my family.”

The availability and accessibility of essential services emerged as another key motivator for the women’s decision to migrate to Ondangwa. Many Respondents emphasized that the absence of critical services such as healthcare, education, and reliable transportation, in their rural hometowns drove them to seek better opportunities in urban areas. As a more developed town, Ondangwa provided access to these vital resources, which were crucial for enhancing their quality of life.

Respondent 3 explained that her decision to move was motivated by:

“Better opportunities such as easy access to the gym, schools closer to the road and houses on serviced land”.

Respondent 8 further expounded the drive to migrate by indicating that:

“I moved here because in my village, it was very hard to get proper medical care when we were sick. The clinic was far, and transportation was expensive, so I decided to move where there is better healthcare.”

5.2 Socio-Economic Constraints

The narratives of migrant women reveal a complex web of cultural expectations and economic dependencies that shape their lives in profound ways. These women, driven by the hope of better opportunities, find themselves navigating a landscape riddled with structural and systemic barriers that impede their ability to integrate fully into urban environments. Their stories are not just personal accounts but reflections of broader societal dynamics that perpetuate inequality and limit upward mobility for women who dare to step outside traditional roles.

Cultural expectations weigh heavily on these women, dictating how they should behave, where they belong, and what opportunities they can access. For Respondent 5, the dream of starting her own salon was thwarted not because she lacked skill or determination, but because she was seen as an outsider.

“I was with one of my aunts, I wanted to stay with her and make my salon, but the people at the market with the space refused because I’m not from here”.

The refusal to grant her space in the market underscores how deeply entrenched notions of belonging and identity can exclude those perceived as ‘other’. This experience is emblematic of larger patterns of social exclusion faced by migrant women, whose aspirations are often dismissed due to biases rooted in regional or ethnic affiliations. Such discrimination reinforces a sense of alienation and denies them the chance to build economic independence.

Similarly, gender-based constraints manifest in both professional and social spheres, shaping what tasks women are deemed capable of performing. Respondent 6’s account of being barred from physically demanding work highlights pervasive stereotypes about women’s physical capabilities.

“I have felt discriminated against. When trucks are offloading goods, I am told that I am not capable of carrying goods so I should focus on customers in the shop though not so often”.

While such restrictions may seem minor in isolation, they contribute to a broader culture of marginalization, limiting women’s roles to predefined categories that align with patriarchal norms. In this way, even seemingly neutral workplace practices become mechanisms of control, reinforcing traditional hierarchies and stifling personal and professional growth.

Economic dependencies further compound these challenges, trapping migrant women in cycles of vulnerability. Long working hours and exploitative labour conditions, as described by Respondent 7, leave little room for rest or self-care, let alone pursuing additional education or entrepreneurial ventures.

“I experienced long working hours{overtime}, I don’t get enough time”

The financial strain of making ends meet forces many women to prioritize immediate survival over long-term goals, perpetuating a cycle of poverty and dependency. For Respondent 4, the lack of start-up capital represents yet another hurdle—a reflection of systemic inequities that disproportionately affect women entrepreneurs.

“I have been thinking of starting up a business but there is no start-up capital, especially for those businesses owned by women”.

Financial institutions and support systems often fail to recognize the potential of businesses owned by women, particularly migrants, leaving them without the resources needed to turn their ideas into reality.

Access to essential resources like housing, healthcare, and education remains elusive for many migrant women, compounding their struggles. Without stable housing, they face constant uncertainty about their living situations, which affects their ability to focus on career advancement or community engagement. Limited access to healthcare exacerbates existing vulnerabilities, while educational opportunities remain out of reach for those juggling multiple responsibilities. These gaps in basic services highlight the interconnected nature of economic and social barriers, creating a domino effect that undermines their agency and autonomy.

These constraints have far-reaching implications for migrant women’s lives. They erode their confidence and diminish their capacity to make independent choices, leaving them dependent on others—whether family members, employers, or local authorities—for survival. The cumulative impact is a loss of agency, where women must constantly negotiate their identities within the confines of societal expectations and economic realities. Their stories underscore the paradox of migration: while it promises freedom and opportunity, it often comes at the cost of enduring new forms of oppression.

5.3 Navigating Social Barriers to Women’s Agency

This theme focuses on the resilience and proactive strategies employed by women to overcome societal limitations and assert their agency. Respondents have demonstrated remarkable adaptability by building networks that fostered mutual support and empowerment, while pursuing economic activities to enhance their independence and financial security.

“Initially, my mother used her pension money to cover my travel expenses. Since I had no relatives in Ondangwa, I stayed with others from my village. The situation was challenging, but we relied on our shared upbringing and mutual support; we grew up together, so we had no choice but to help each other” (R. 5)

But also

“... I joined a women’s cooperative and started to sell vegetables in the market” (R. 10)

Respondent 8 echoed such sentiment explaining how the lack of educational opportunities restricted her from getting stable employment, but:

“Because of lack of educational skills, I was unable to be employed but I was helped by other women to start up my business”.

On the other hand, all respondents were fully aware of their rights emphasising the need of supportive policies and social programs aimed at promoting gender equality and employment opportunities.

“Women should be provided with the necessary resources and support to advocate for their rights, enabling them to take charge of their lives and futures”, (R. 8).

Similarly, Respondent 12 advocated for a broader approach to social programs and policy reforms, noting the necessity of addressing both structural and societal issues:

Different programs and policies should be established to relieve multiple social constraints that women face in the society as well as find different ways to address attitudes as well as matters concerning gender inequality or discrimination of women in the society”.

These efforts reflect a broader movement toward challenging traditional norms and creating spaces where women can thrive both socially and economically. By engaging in advocacy, building supportive networks, and leveraging social programs, women embody the spirit of Ubuntu, empowering themselves while fostering empowerment within their communities.

Furthermore, migrant women highlighted the need for women to network and build relationships with other women in the community as this will strengthen their advocacy, gain them support in fighting for their rights and enable them to have faster access to things such as job opportunities or training for business starters. Such networks not only ensure emotional encouragement but also enable access to financial support and business advice that will aid migrant women in pushing through the constraints they face. Additional another important element that was highlighted is community education and training initiatives that would play a critical role in empowerment women on how to run their businesses in the best ways possible and help them improve their skills to become better suited to different employment opportunities.

Despite facing numerous challenges, the findings highlight the resilience and resourcefulness of migrant women in Ondangwa. These women employ a variety of adaptive strategies to overcome adversity and reshape their social realities. Respondents emphasized the significance of shared knowledge, collaboration, and collective action in tackling difficulties and fostering resilience. These observations align with Kinyanjui (2020), who underscores the critical role that communal networks and solidarity play in empowering migrant women within African urban spaces. Furthermore, literature by O’Neil et al. (2016) and Chant and Pedwell (2008) supports the view that collective action and social networking are essential mechanisms through which marginalized women can challenge social constraints and secure greater agency.

Drawing inspiration from Ubuntu principles centered on interconnectedness, mutual care, and collective responsibility the study argues that these cultural values enable women to challenge restrictive social norms and assert their agency (Nussbaum, 2003). Migrant women in Ondangwa leverage informal support networks, engage in micro-entrepreneurship, advocate for the creation of women’s groups, and community-based organizations to navigate social and economic barriers. These strategies mirror findings by Adepoju, (2008), who highlights that informal networks and entrepreneurial efforts are key coping mechanisms for migrant women across sub-Saharan Africa.

However, systemic barriers such as entrenched gender biases, discriminatory practices in employment and public services, and the absence of gender-responsive policies (International Labour Organisation, 2020). continue to limit the full realization of Ubuntu’s ideals of inclusivity and shared humanity. The dynamic interplay between social constraints and the agency power of migrant women in Ondangwa reveals a complex environment in which women must continuously negotiate their positions within both public and private spheres. The study underscores the importance of recognizing and supporting women’s agency as a cornerstone for fostering inclusive and equitable societies. Respondents strongly emphasized that addressing the root causes of marginalization, such as poverty, gender discrimination, and limited access to education and financial resources, is essential. By implementing targeted interventions and policies that promote economic empowerment, inclusive governance, and gender-sensitive institutional reforms, policymakers and stakeholders can create an enabling environment where migrant women are

empowered to thrive. Their contributions can extend beyond personal advancement to the broader socio-economic development of their host communities

6. Conclusion

These networks reflect Ubuntu's emphasis on collective resilience and mutual aid, offering emotional, social, and economic support in times of need. Consequently, Ubuntu serves as both a moral framework and a blueprint for social organisation, profoundly embedded in African cultures and ideologies.

This study advances critical dialogues at the intersection of gender, migration, and empowerment by examining how female migrants in sub-Saharan Africa negotiate and challenge structural barriers redefining societal norms. Focusing on Namibia, the research reveals nuanced motivations behind women's migration to Ondangwa. Findings indicate that migration is driven by economic precarity, limited access to resources, and aspirational mobility, with many women viewing Ondangwa as a site of relative opportunity for livelihoods and entrepreneurship. While the town offers avenues for economic participation, ultimately, the experiences of these women reveal the urgent need to address the structural and systemic barriers that hinder their integration and empowerment. Cultural norms, economic dependencies, and discriminatory practices converge to create a hostile environment where migrant women struggle to assert their rights and achieve their aspirations. By centring their voices and recognizing the intersections of gender, migration status, and socio-economic background, we can begin to dismantle the systems that perpetuate inequality. Only then can we move toward a future where migrant women are no longer marginalized but empowered to shape their destinies with dignity and resilience.

To reimagine pathways for agency, this paper engages Ubuntu philosophy, an African ethical paradigm rooted in relational ontology, communal reciprocity, and the interdependence of human dignity. At its core, Ubuntu emphasizes relational ontology, communal reciprocity, and the interconnectedness of human dignity, presenting an alternative to the atomistic individualism often embedded in Western frameworks. By centring Ubuntu's ethos in both policy design and community initiatives, we can create systems that prioritize collective well-being over isolated self-interest, fostering environments where migrant women are not merely passive recipients of aid but active co-creators of equitable societies.

One practical recommendation is the intentional strengthening and formalization of solidarity networks, which already play a vital role in the lives of many migrant women. These networks—rooted in shared experiences, trust, and mutual support—epitomize Ubuntu's spirit of collaborative resilience. For example, by institutionalizing support systems that mirror these organic networks, governments and organizations can amplify their impact. This could involve establishing cooperatives or community hubs where migrant women have access to resources such as microloans, legal assistance, and skill-building workshops. Such initiatives would not only provide tangible tools for economic empowerment but also reinforce the communal bonds central to Ubuntu's philosophy, enabling women to navigate systemic barriers collectively rather than in isolation.

Another pathway lies in redefining leadership and decision-making processes within institutions to reflect Ubuntu's values of inclusivity and shared responsibility. Migrant women should be actively included in forums where policies affecting their lives are designed and implemented. Their voices must move from the margins to the centre, ensuring that solutions are culturally grounded and contextually relevant. For instance, advisory boards or participatory governance models could be established, comprising representatives from migrant communities who collaborate with policymakers. This approach aligns with Ubuntu's emphasis on personhood being cultivated through relationships and collective action, positioning migrant women as architects of change rather than mere beneficiaries of externally imposed interventions.

Furthermore, addressing the extractive tendencies of global energy transitions requires embedding Ubuntu's principles into international partnerships and agreements. Instead of perpetuating colonial legacies under the guise of green progress, renewable energy projects in Africa—and elsewhere—must adopt frameworks that prioritize local ownership and benefit-sharing. This could involve mandating joint ventures between foreign investors and local communities, ensuring that profits and decision-making power remain within the regions where resources are extracted. By doing so, these projects honour Ubuntu's commitment to interdependence and equity, transforming exploitative dynamics into opportunities for sustainable development that uplift entire communities.

Education and advocacy also hold immense potential as vehicles for transformation when infused with Ubuntu's ethos. Community-driven awareness campaigns can challenge entrenched patriarchal norms and cultural expectations that restrict women's agency. For example, storytelling circles or dialogues led by migrant women themselves can serve as platforms for sharing experiences, challenging stereotypes, and reshaping societal perceptions about gender roles. These efforts align with Ubuntu's focus on collective learning and mutual growth, creating spaces where women are affirmed in their identities and empowered to redefine societal narratives around migration, work, and leadership.

Finally, integrating Ubuntu into broader policy frameworks offers a way to bridge the disconnection between social justice and sustainability. By weaving this philosophy into the fabric of policy and practice, we can catalyse transformative change that honours the interconnectedness of all people, paving the way for truly equitable societies.

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